

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF COMPLEX METALLIC FERRO AND FERRICYANIDES. PART V. POTENTIOMETRIC STUDY OF THE COMPOSITION OF CADMIUM FERROCYANIDE USING THE FERRO-FERRICYANIDE ELECTRODES

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The ferro-ferricyanide electrode has been employed in the potentiometric study of the composition of cadmium ferrocyanide. The results support the conclusions derived from the thermometric titrations in the formation of the compound $K_2CdFeCy_6$ and the influence of hydrolysis and adsorption in its precipitation (*cf* Part IV).

The oxidation potential of the ferro-ferricyanide electrode according to the equation,

is given by

$$E = E_0 + 0.059 \log \frac{(FeCy_6)^{III}}{(FeCy_6)^{IV}} \quad (25^\circ).$$

As in the potentiometric study of copper ferrocyanide using the ferro-ferricyanide electrode (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 25, 27) the titrating solution is potassium ferrocyanide containing 1% potassium ferricyanide with a platinised platinum electrode used in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode. So long as there is an excess of cadmium ions in the solution, the concentration of ferrocyanide ions being small, the potential of the electrode is high. As soon as the cadmium ions are quantitatively precipitated, the next drop of ferrocyanide solution causes a sudden increase in $(FeCy_6)^{IV}$, and hence a sudden decrease in the oxidation potential occurs. This corresponds to the equivalence point.

EXPERIMENTAL

Standard solutions were prepared as described in part IV of this series (*this issue*, p. 185). The titrations were made using different concentrations of the titrant. $M/5.0$ solution of potassium ferrocyanide would be referred as A/1 solution of potassium ferrocyanide, and $M/5.41$ solution of cadmium sulphate as A/1 solution of $CdSO_4$.

TABLE I

A/10- $CdSO_4$ soln. = 20 c.c. (Fig. 1).

A/2- K_4FeCy_6 added.	$E_{obs.}$						
0.0 c.c.	0.4428 volt	1.9 c.c.	0.3166 volt	3.2 c.c.	0.3055 volt	4.0 c.c.	0.1212 volt
0.5	0.3340	2.0	0.3156	3.4	0.2995	4.1	0.1140
1.0	0.3278	2.2	0.3136	3.5	0.2905	4.2	0.1090
1.2	0.3268	2.4	0.3116	3.6	0.2885	4.3	0.1040
1.4	0.3227	2.6	0.3096	3.7	0.1854	4.4	0.0916
1.6	0.3207	2.8	0.3075	3.8	0.1466	4.5	0.0960
1.8	0.3176	3.0	0.3070	3.9	0.1318	4.6	0.0920

TABLE II

A/10-CdSO₄ soln. = 20 c.c. (Fig. 2).

A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	E _{obs.}	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	E _{obs.}	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	E _{obs.}	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	E _{obs.}
0.0 c.c.	0.3410 volt	2.8 c.c.	0.3248 volt	5.6 c.c.	0.3075 volt	7.6 c.c.	0.1303 volt
0.4	0.3448	3.2	0.3223	6.0	0.3025	7.8	0.1190
0.8	0.3348	3.6	0.3200	6.4	0.3000	8.0	0.1130
1.2	0.3332	4.0	0.3176	6.8	0.2970	8.2	0.1040
1.6	0.3312	4.4	0.3155	7.0	0.3050	8.4	0.1000
2.0	0.3292	4.8	0.3125	7.2	0.2260	8.6	0.0970
2.4	0.3263	5.2	0.3104	7.4	0.1527		

TABLE III

A/10-CdSO₄ = 20 c.c. (Fig. 3).

A/8-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	E _{obs.}	A/8-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	E _{obs.}	A/8-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	E _{obs.}	A/8-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	E _{obs.}
0.0 c.c.	0.3512 volt	6.0 c.c.	0.3181 volt	11.5 c.c.	0.2870 volt	15.0 c.c.	0.2890 volt
1.0	0.3471	7.0	0.3054	12.0	0.2820	15.5	0.2015
2.0	0.3360	8.0	0.3003	12.5	0.2180	16.0	0.1476
3.0	0.3354	9.0	0.2910	13.0	0.2740	16.5	0.1293
4.0	0.3027	10.0	0.2870	13.5	0.2688	17.0	0.1171
5.0	0.3175	11.0	0.2932	14.0	0.2748	18.0	0.1070
							0.0880

TABLE IV

Results of the potentiometric titrations.

K ₄ FeCy ₆ .	CdSO ₄ .	Observed titre value for 20 c.c. of A/10 soln.	Equiv. vol. of A/10-K ₄ FeCy ₆ .	Curve No.
A/2	A/10	3.68 c.c.	18.4 c.c.	1
A/4	A/10	7.24	18.1	2
A/8	A/10	14.40	18.0	3

DISCUSSION

Considering the strengths of the solutions of potassium ferrocyanide (*M*/5.0) and cadmium sulphate (*M*/5.41) the theoretical titre value for 20 c.c. of cadmium sulphate solution for the formation of the compound K₂CdFeCy₆ is 18.5 c.c. of potassium ferrocyanide solution. Compounds Cd₂FeCy₆ and K₂Cd₃(FeCy₆)₂ require respectively 9.25 and 12.32 c.c. of potassium ferrocyanide solution.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

The observed titre value is slightly lower than the theoretical one required for the formation of the compound $K_2CdFeCy_6$. This discrepancy between the observed and the theoretical titre value can be explained, as has been previously done (Part IV, *loc. cit.*) by considering the hydrolysable character of this compound and the influence of adsorption on its precipitation. Potassium ferrocyanide, released as a result of hydrolysis of the compound, would react with some cadmium sulphate, resulting in a

lowering of the observed titre value than the theoretical one. The adsorption of Cd^{++} ions by the precipitate would also tend to lower the observed titre values. A decrease in titre value with the increase of dilution is observed. This clearly shows that the extent of hydrolysis increases with the dilution.

As in the case of copper ferrocyanide, potentiometric titrations could not be carried in the presence of alcohol (which had been possible in the thermometric studies of the compound in Part IV of this series), because constant values of potential could not then be obtained.

Potentiometric studies support the thermometric conclusions regarding the formation of the compound $\text{K}_2\text{CdFeCy}_6$ and the important role of hydrolysis and adsorption in its precipitation.

The conductometric studies on the composition of the compound are in progress, and will be communicated shortly.

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